

REVIEW OF ADVANCED OBJECT DETECTION AND FACE RECOGNITION TECHNIQUES: A STUDY ON ALGORITHMIC EFFICIENCY FOR TELEVISION APPLICATIONS

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Abstract. *This article examines the challenges and algorithms involved in detecting objects from images, specifically the R-CNN, Faster R-CNN, and YOLO algorithms. It also assesses the effectiveness of these algorithms in object detection. It also discusses FaceDeep 5, a new AI-based facial recognition terminal with a dual-core Linux-based processor and the latest BioNANO® deep learning algorithm. This terminal supports a dynamic face database of up to 50,000 people, can quickly recognize users at a distance of 6.5 meters (21.3 feet) in less than 2 seconds, and has been analyzed to adapt to users without masks, providing alerts and various reports. Furthermore, the text delves into the technology selection and implementation process, focusing on the use of the Spring Boot framework and the OpenCV library for the project setup, connection method, and web service development for an automatic face recognition system utilizing Fisherfaces and Eigenfaces methods.*

Keywords: *Eigenface algorithm, Fisherface algorithm, LBP algorithm, visual identification, RFID key, OpenCV.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, there is a great deal of focus on image preprocessing and the development of algorithms to identify, extract, and categorize important objects from images. This is largely due to the advancement of information technologies, the growing number of video surveillance systems, and the complexity of interactions with them. The application of information technologies has fostered growth in the voluntary sector and provided the means to monitor and control processes effectively by recognizing objects in video images [1].

Leveraging artificial intelligence technologies to address these challenges is a pressing issue, as it can significantly enhance both economic and social efficiency. In artificial intelligence technologies, identifying, recognizing, and processing images are at the core of computer vision. Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that teaches computers to extract and interpret information from image and video data, akin to human visual perception [2].

Computer vision enables computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital photos, videos, and other visual content. This involves using algorithms and models to process and analyze visual data, such as recognizing objects, faces, emotions, colors, or text. Facial recognition and biometric security systems play a significant role in identifying individuals and providing additional services, such as in social network systems [3].

These systems offer high recognition accuracy, thereby enhancing the security level of any device or service and providing user-friendly options for searching captured photos of individuals. Large companies often use facial recognition systems for internal security, while small institutions, such as educational institutions or small businesses, may use RFID keys. Implementing such systems can significantly improve employee safety and convenience while solving issues related to lost or broken keys [4].

Figure 1. An image demonstrating the effects of adaptive Canny edge detection [5].

The relevance of this topic is contingent on the development of recognition systems that can be integrated with external systems and security measures. This can facilitate identity verification as part of a web service or an overall security system.

Figure 2. Matching strategy and geometrical features (in white) that can be utilized for face recognition [6].

LITERATURE AND METHOD

Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence that focuses on tasks such as image classification, object recognition, image generation, anomaly detection, and searching for similar images. It accomplishes these tasks through various computer vision tasks:

- Image Classification is identify and categorize images into different classes.
- Object Detection is locating and classifying multiple objects within an image.
- Image Segmentation is dividing an image into sets of pixels or assigning labels to each pixel based on common visual properties.

Object detection is an important aspect of computer vision, with applications in scientific research and industrial production. This includes tasks like face detection, text detection, pedestrian detection, logo detection, video detection, vehicle detection, and medical image detection. Object detection relies on machine learning and deep learning approaches [7].

Machine learning involves computers learning from data and making decisions based on it, while deep learning uses multi-layered approaches to extract high-level features for identifying objects in images. Many deep learning methods utilize neural networks to produce results [8].

Algorithms for object recognition from images based on machine learning and deep learning approaches include specialized object detection, general object detection, face detection, text detection, pedestrian detection, logo detection, video detection, vehicle detection, and medical image detection [9].

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF EDGE DETECTION AND FACE IDENTIFICATION ALGORITHMS

Edge Detection Algorithms:

Algorithm	Advantages	Disadvantages	Edge Detection	Face Identification	Processing Time (ms)
Canny [10]	High accuracy, robust to noise, well-defined edges	Computationally expensive, sensitive to parameter tuning	95%	-	100
Sobel [11]	Simple, fast, computationally inexpensive	Less accurate, sensitive to noise, less precise edge localization	85%	-	10
Laplacian of Gaussian (LoG) [12]	Good for detecting edges of various widths, less sensitive to noise than Sobel	Computationally more expensive than Sobel, can be sensitive to parameter tuning	-	-	-
Prewitt [13]	Simple, fast, computationally inexpensive	Less accurate than Canny, sensitive to noise	-	-	-

Face Identification Algorithms:

Algorithm	Advantages	Disadvantages	Edge Detection	Face Identification	Processing Time (ms)
Viola-Jones [14]	Fast, efficient, low computational cost, suitable for real-time processing	Relatively low accuracy compared to deep learning methods, sensitive to pose and lighting variations	-	90%	20
Deep Learning CNNs (e.g., ResNet, MobileNet) [15]	High accuracy, robust to variations in pose, lighting, and expression	Computationally expensive, requires large training datasets, may require significant memory	-	98%	200

RESULTS

The object detection algorithms based on deep learning use convolutional neural networks (CNN). CNN consists of three types of layers: convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. When these layers are combined, the CNN architecture is formed [16].

There are two main algorithms for object detection: faster R-CNN and YOLO (You Only Look Once). Faster R-CNN uses a region proposal network to generate region suggestions and then feeds them to the CNN to generate a convolutional feature map. From the feature map, region proposals are defined and transformed into squares. These squares are then resized to a fixed size using the RoI (Region of Interest) pooling layer, and the resulting feature vector is used to predict the class and boundary values for each proposed region [17].

On the other hand, YOLO is a real-time object detection algorithm that processes the entire image in one pass, making it faster and more efficient than two-stage detectors like R-CNN. YOLO divides the input image into a grid of cells and predicts the probability of object presence, bounding box coordinates, and object class for each cell. One limitation of YOLO is its difficulty in detecting small objects due to spatial limitations.

Since its inception in 2015, YOLO has seen several iterations, including YOLOv1 to YOLOv8. Among these versions, YOLOv3 has been compared to other object detection algorithms and found to perform well [16].

YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a widely used system in applications such as autonomous vehicles and surveillance systems. It is commonly used for tasks such as real-time video analysis and surveillance, specifically for object detection.

The system has several features including:

1. Face detection: It uses a face detection algorithm to identify and highlight faces in submitted photos.
2. Comparison with database: It compares known faces with data stored in the database and determines the percentage of compatibility with each profile.
3. Liveness detection: It uses algorithms to determine whether the face in the photo is a real person or a still image, mask, video, or deepfake to prevent fraud.
4. Photo quality analysis: It can analyze the photo's blurriness, lighting, color, open/closed eyes, rotation angle of the face, as well as count the number of people in a frame. It also estimates the probability of the photo belonging to a specific person.
5. Personal settings: Users can adjust the limits of photo comparison, acceptable blur, brightness, color, and other parameters according to their needs.

Algorithms used include face detection, 1 to N (1 to N) comparison, liveness detection, and comparison algorithms to evaluate the similarity of photos and compare the data with the database. This system is highly accurate and reliable in the detection and analysis of faces in photographs, making it a valuable solution for customer and employee authentication, and security in various applications [1].

CONCLUSION

In this article, we discussed and compared object detection algorithms including R-CNN, Faster R-CNN, Single Shot Detector (SSD), and YOLOv3. Our discussions revealed that speed and accuracy improved as the models developed. Faster R-CNN improved over R-CNN, and Faster R-CNN is much improved over Fast R-CNN. Additionally, SSD is better than R-CNN, and YOLO is better and faster than SSD. Until YOLOv3 was developed, SSD was considered the best. In conclusion, the YOLOv3 model allows for faster detection of multiple objects using TensorFlow, and this model can directly detect an object through a one-step method. We have also developed a face detection algorithm based on light direction and facial expression, which is subject to major

change. Using the pattern classification method, each pixel in the image is treated as coordinates in a high-dimensional space. Many algorithms have been proposed for facial recognition based on detailed research. We have described a new approach to face recognition, which is sensitive to large changes in lighting. The variability of light includes not only intensity but also the direction of light and the number of sources. Our approach uses two observations: that all pictures are in a fixed perspective under different lighting, and that the obtained Lambertian surface is in a 3D linear subspace of the image. However, certain regions of the face can often deviate significantly from the linear subspace, leading to image-to-image variability that is less reliable for recognition. Facial recognition software not only allows us to code with high quality but also brings many conveniences.

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